

An ethogram for Equitation Science's First Principles of Horse Training

Equitation Science Principle	Behaviour
1. Train according to the horse's ethology and cognition	1.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating how horses require (a) the company of other horses (b) movement (c) virtually continuous eating OR that anthropomorphism should be avoided. 1.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 1.1.
2. Use learning theory appropriately	2.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating the use of: (a) habituation / desensitisation (b) sensitisation (c) the four possible consequences of operant conditioning (d) shaping and (e) classical conditioning. 2.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 2.1.
3. Train easy-to-discriminate signals	3.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating the use of unique and easily discriminated signals to cue required behaviours. 3.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 3.1.
4. Shape responses and movements	4.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating the shaping of a required behaviour by reinforcing gradually improving approximations of that behaviour. 4.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 4.1.
5. Elicit responses one-at-a-time	5.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that individual cues/signals should be separated in time from each other and should not elicit conflicting responses (for example: acceleration and deceleration). 5.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 5.1.
6. Train only one response per signal	6.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that each cue should elicit a single response. 6.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 6.1.
7. Form consistent habits	7.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that training contexts / environments should (initially) be consistent, until the required responses are consolidated. 7.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 7.1.
8. Train persistence of responses (self-carriage)	8.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that the horse should keep going in response to a cue /signal, without the need for constant repetition of cues, which the horse may habituate to. 8.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 8.1.
9. Avoid and dissociate flight responses (because they resist extinction and trigger fear problems)	9.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that flight responses should be avoided. 9.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 9.1.
10. Demonstrate minimum levels of arousal sufficient for training (to ensure absence of conflict)	10.1 CORRECTLY describing or demonstrating that only minimum required levels of arousal for task should be trained and that the horse should be as relaxed as possible. 10.2 INCORRECTLY describing or demonstrating 10.1.